

Conductance Behaviour of Potassium and Silver Dodecyl Sulphates in Polar Solvents

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The critical micelle concentrations of potassium and silver dodecyl sulphates in lower alcohols, alcohol-water and alcohol-benzene mixtures were determined conductometrically. The conductance data have been used to calculate the thermodynamic parameters of micellization.

CONDUCTANCE behaviour of metal dodecyl sulphates in aqueous medium has been studied by several workers¹⁻¹². However, data on their solution behaviour in alkanols are not reported. There has been a controversy in solution behaviour of surfactants in alkanols. Several authors suggest the presence of micelles¹³⁻¹⁷ of surfactants in solutions in alkanols while some others have commented on absence of micelles^{18,19}. In this paper we have examined the micellar behaviour of silver and potassium dodecyl sulphates in lower alkanols, alkanol-water and alkanol-benzene mixtures of varying compositions by conductivity method.

Experimental

Extra-pure sodium dodecyl sulphate was used for preparation of silver and potassium salts¹¹. Reagent grade chemicals were used throughout the experiment. Conductivity water ($K \sim 1 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) was taken. Conductance measurements were carried out using Philips conductivity bridge at constant temperature. The conductivity data were reproducible to 0.1%.

Results and Discussion

The CMC values of metal dodecyl sulphates in different alkanols (methanol, propan-1-ol, propan-2-ol and butan-1-ol) over the temperature range (35-50°) were determined from the intersection of two straight line portions of the specific conductance (K) vs concentration (C) plots (a representative set of curves is shown in Fig. 1) and are recorded in Tables 1 and 2. Studies on potassium dodecyl sulphate in propan-1-ol and propan-2-ol could not be carried out owing to its low solubility in these alkanols. The CMC values increase with increase in temperature but decrease with increasing carbon

Fig. 1. Specific conductance vs concentration plots for silver dodecyl sulphate in propan-1-ol at different temperatures.

number in the alkanols used as solvent. The CMC values of potassium dodecyl sulphate were higher than those for silver dodecyl sulphate.

The aggregation of potassium dodecyl sulphate in methanol-water and methanol-benzene mixtures of different compositions was also studied and the CMC values obtained from $K-C$ plots are recorded in Table 3. The CMC values were found independent of water concentration for methanol-water

TABLE 1—VALUES OF CMC, CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR METAL DODECYL SULPHATES IN POLAR SOLVENTS

System	CMC × 10 ⁴ mol l ⁻¹	Temperature 40°		λ_{∞} $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ eq ⁻¹	K × 10 ⁴ $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	-ΔG _D ⁰ kcal	-ΔG _A ⁰ kcal
		A	B				
KDS							
Methanol	3.10	1.615	0.125	—	—	—	11.40
Butan-1-ol	2.20	1.550	0.400	12.00	6.25	4.59	10.86
AgDS							
Methanol	3.00	1.745	0.750	—	—	—	11.52
Propan-1-ol	2.80	0.930	0.390	34.90	9.02	4.36	10.82
Propan-2-ol	2.00	1.970	0.400	27.50	3.90	4.88	11.94
Butan-1-ol	1.40	1.870	0.400	—	—	—	11.42

mixtures and the identical values obtained were in between the CMC in water and methanol²⁰. However, the CMC was found to decrease with increasing amount of benzene in methanol-benzene mixtures. The decreasing trend in CMC for methanol-benzene mixture has been depicted in Fig. 2. Such a decrease in CMC of surfactant with increasing benzene content in the solvent mixture appears due to the decreasing polar character of the solvent. Figs. 3 and 4 represent plots of the specific conductance vs volume % of additives in methanol. In

Fig. 2. Log CMC vs volume % benzene for potassium dodecyl sulphate in methanol-benzene mixture.

Fig. 3. Specific conductance vs volume % benzene for potassium dodecyl sulphate in methanol-benzene mixtures: (1) 0.0050, (2) 0.0045, (3) 0.0040, (4) 0.0035, (5) 0.0030, (6) 0.0020 and (7) 0.0010 mol l⁻¹.

Fig. 3 the conductance data seem to acquire a limiting value at 50% benzene. Conductivity of surfactant solution with higher volume % was not determined for physical in significance. However, Fig. 4 shows that the specific conductance initially decreases with the addition of water up to 40% and then increase with further addition. It may therefore be suggested that a change in the nature of solvent occurs at about 50% composition for both the solvents.

Fig. 4. Specific conductance vs volume % water for potassium dodecyl sulphate in methanol-water mixtures: (1) 0.0050, (2) 0.0045, (3) 0.0040, (4) 0.0035, (5) 0.0030, (6) 0.0020, (7) 0.0010 mol l⁻¹.

The conductance behaviour of both the surfactants in the system has been satisfactorily expressed by the equation²¹

$$\log \lambda = A + B \log C.$$

The values of constants A and B evaluated by extrapolating $\log \lambda$ vs $\log C$ plot (Fig. 5) are recorded in Tables 1-3. The values of constant A which signify limiting molar conductance have got theoretical importance, since it is not possible to prepare molar soap solutions owing to their low solubility. The trend in the change of constants A and B at 50% volume in solvent mixture is likely due to the changing nature of solvent which causes changes in the nature of micelles from alcomicelles to hy-

Fig. 5. Log molecular conductance vs log concentration for silver dodecyl sulphate in propan-1-ol : (1) 50°, (2) 45°, (3) 40° and (4) 35°.

dromicelles (in alkanol-water mixture), and alcomicelles to oleomicelles (in alkanol-benzene mixture). Such a change in behaviour of solvent has also been observed previously.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF CMC AND OTHER CONSTANTS FOR SILVER DODECYL SULPHATE IN PROPAN-1-OL

Temperature °C	CMC × 10 ³ mol l ⁻¹	A	B	λ _∞ Ω ⁻¹ cm ² eq ⁻¹	K × 10 ⁴ cm ⁻¹
35	2.60	0.300	0.325	31.90	9.56
40	2.80	0.330	0.330	34.90	9.02
45	3.00	0.350	0.335	36.90	8.80
50	3.20	0.380	0.340	41.60	7.98

Since these surfactants in alkanols behave like weak electrolytes, the expression for their dissociation can be derived^{2,2}.

$$C(1-\alpha) = C\alpha = C\alpha$$

$$K = \frac{C\alpha^2}{(1-\alpha)}$$

Where α is the degree of dissociation and K the dissociation constant. Since α in such systems is very small, interionic effects may be treated as negligible. Thus considering α as λ_M/λ_∞ :

$$C\lambda_M = \frac{K\lambda_\infty^2}{\lambda_M} - K\lambda_\infty$$

The plots of $C\lambda_M$ vs $1/\lambda_M$ are linear (Fig. 6) below CMC except for methanol and methanol-benzene systems where the plots are not linear. However, the equation fails above the CMC as the process of

Fig. 6. $C\lambda_M$ vs $1/\lambda_M$ for silver dodecyl sulphate in propan-1-ol : ● 50°, ○ 45°, □ 40° and ■ 35°.

aggregation takes place. The dissociation constant (K) and the molar conductance at infinite dilution (λ_∞) for both the surfactants in different solvent systems were evaluated from the slopes and intercepts of the above plots and are recorded in Tables 1-3. Further, the heat of dissociation for silver dodecyl sulphate in propan-1-ol obtained from the linear slopes of $\log K$ vs $1/T$ plots (Fig. 7) is -2.28 kcal.

The free energy for the dissociation process, ΔG_D was evaluated from the expression^{2,3,24}

$$\Delta G_D^0 = -RT \ln K_A$$

TABLE 3—VALUES OF CMC, CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR POTASSIUM DODECYL SULPHATE IN MIXTURES

System	CMC × 10 ³ mol l ⁻¹	Temperature 40°			K × 10 ⁴ Ω ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	-ΔG _D ⁰ kcal	-ΔG _A ⁰ kcal
		A	B	λ _∞ Ω ⁻¹ cm ² eq ⁻¹			
Water in methanol							
20%	5.50	1.595	0.110	96.70	0.95	2.90	10.94
40%	5.50	1.545	0.100	80.00	0.93	2.91	11.10
50%	5.50	1.630	0.085	81.34	1.65	2.55	11.16
60%	5.50	1.670	0.075	86.00	1.74	2.52	11.24
80%	5.50	1.720	0.070	97.87	2.40	2.32	11.34
Benzene in methanol							
10%	2.500	1.460	0.170	—	—	—	11.66
20%	2.325	1.410	0.170	—	—	—	11.66
30%	2.175	1.350	0.170	—	—	—	11.66
40%	1.980	1.255	0.175	—	—	—	11.70
50%	1.825	0.880	0.260	—	—	—	11.70
60%	1.625	0.395	0.360	—	—	—	11.72

Fig. 7. Log K and log CMC_M vs 1/T for silver dodecyl sulphate in propan-1-ol.

where K_A is the equilibrium constant for association process^{23,24}.

Again, $\Delta G_D^0 = -RT \ln 1/K_D = RT \ln K_D$

Where K_D is the equilibrium constant for dissociation process, i.e. dissociation constant.

Now for aggregation process, when counter ions are bound to the micelle, the standard free energy of micellization (per mole of monomer), ΔG_A^0 , for the phase separation model is given by the expression²⁵

$$\Delta G_A^0 = 2RT \ln CMC_M$$

Where CMC_M is expressed as a mole fraction and where the total number of moles present at the CMC is equal to the sum of moles of solvent and surfactant. The free energies for the dissociation and micellization processes for the system are recorded in Tables 1-3.

Again, the standard enthalpy change of micellization (ΔH_A^0) per mole of monomer from the same approach²⁵ is given by

$$\frac{\delta}{\delta T} \ln CMC_M = \frac{\Delta H_A^0}{RT^2}$$

$$\text{or } \ln CMC_M = \frac{\Delta H_A^0}{RT} + C$$

ΔH_A^0 for silver dodecyl sulphate in propan-1-ol has been calculated from the linear plot of log CMC_M vs 1/T (Fig. 7) and is +2.75 kcal. This value indicates that the net energy involved in the micellization process is greater than that involved for dissociation of surfactants. This is also in accordance with the free energy data for dissociation and micellization of surfactants in all other systems.

The standard entropy changes for dissociation and micellization processes ΔS_D^0 and ΔS_A^0 for silver

dodecyl sulphate in propan-1-ol were evaluated using the expression

$$\Delta S^0 = \frac{\Delta H^0 - \Delta G^0}{T}$$

ΔG^0 and ΔS^0 values for dissociation and micellization processes have been plotted against the temperature (Fig. 8). The $\Delta G_{A,D}^0$ values increase linearly with temperature and CMC_M (Fig. 9). On the other hand, a linear decrease/increase was seen in $\Delta S_A^0/\Delta S_D^0$ values. Furthermore, ΔS^0 values for micellization process were also higher than the values of ΔS^0 for dissociation.

Fig. 8. Free energy (and entropy) vs temperature of silver dodecyl sulphate in propan-1-ol: \circ : ΔG_D , \square : ΔS_D , \bullet : ΔG_A and \blacksquare : ΔS_A .

Fig. 9. Free energy (and entropy) vs CMC_M of silver dodecyl sulphate in propan-1-ol: \circ : ΔG_D , \square : ΔS_D , \bullet : ΔG_A and \blacksquare : ΔS_A .

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